

Teacher Retention and Satisfaction in Private Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study examined teacher retention and job satisfaction in selected private schools in the Schools Division of Silay City during School Year 2025–2026. It focused on compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth as shared organizational conditions influencing teachers' satisfaction and decision to stay. An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was used. In the quantitative phase, purposive sampling was employed, and all 78 teachers who met the inclusion criteria in the selected schools were included in the study. Data were analyzed using weighted mean, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression. In the qualitative phase, 15 teachers were selected through maximum variation sampling and interviewed using a semi-structured guide. Interview data were transcribed, organized through a manual coding matrix, and analyzed thematically to explain the survey results. Findings showed a high level of teacher retention across all four areas and a high level of teacher satisfaction overall, although satisfaction with compensation was only moderate. At the bivariate level, compensation and administrative support showed significant positive relationships with retention. In the regression model, all four satisfaction dimensions significantly predicted retention, with professional growth emerging as the strongest predictor. Qualitative findings showed that teachers' long-term commitment was shaped not only by school conditions but also by student-related fulfillment, belonging, vocational purpose, and work–life sustainability. The study concludes that teacher retention in private schools is multidimensional and is better strengthened through coordinated institutional support. The findings informed the development of a Faculty Development Plan that includes compensation review, leadership dialogue, professional growth opportunities, enhanced working conditions, and continuous feedback mechanisms.

Keywords: Administrative support, job satisfaction, private schools, professional growth, teacher retention

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INTRODUCTION

Teachers are central to school quality, learner progress, and institutional stability. When schools retain capable teachers, they preserve instructional continuity, strengthen school culture, and reduce the cost of repeated hiring and adjustment. Across education systems, teacher retention remains a concern because burnout, workload pressure, and weak institutional support can weaken long-term commitment (UNESCO, 2022; Toropova et al., 2021). In private schools, the issue is often more complex because teachers work within tighter financial and organizational conditions.

In the Philippine setting, retention concerns are especially visible in private schools, where lower pay, limited benefits, and heavier role demands may weaken long-term commitment (Cañete & Calingasan, 2023; Oducado et al., 2021). These concerns may become more serious in provincial schools, particularly smaller institutions that operate with limited resources and require teachers to handle multiple responsibilities (Tarrayo & Duque, 2022). As a result, retention is not only a staffing issue. It is also a question of teacher well-being, professional commitment, and instructional continuity.

Related studies consistently identify compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth as important conditions that shape both teacher satisfaction and retention (Anog et al., 2024; Eryilmaz et al., 2025; Ramirez, 2024; Ubal, 2025). These same conditions can be interpreted through Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Social Exchange Theory. Herzberg's framework suggests that compensation, administrative support, and working conditions operate as foundational workplace conditions, while professional growth functions as a motivator that deepens commitment (Herzberg et al., 1959). Social Exchange Theory further explains that when teachers experience fair and supportive treatment, they are more likely to respond with trust, commitment, and willingness to stay (Blau, 1964).

What remains insufficiently examined is how these four shared conditions shape both teacher satisfaction and teacher retention at the same time within provincial private schools, and how teachers themselves explain these patterns. Many Philippine studies focus on public schools, urban settings, or one outcome at a time, which leaves school leaders with limited evidence for local and integrated action (Lagura & Caleja, 2024). This study addressed that gap through an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design in selected private schools in Silay City. It contributes to theory by examining the joint relevance of Herzberg's and Blau's frameworks in a private-school setting, contributes to practice by providing evidence for a Faculty Development Plan, and contributes to policy by offering local guidance for teacher-support strategies in private basic education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to answer the following objectives:

1. determine the level of teacher retention in terms of compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth;
2. determine the level of teacher satisfaction in terms of compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth;
3. examine the relationship between teacher satisfaction and teacher retention across the four areas;
4. describe teachers' lived experiences related to satisfaction and retention;
5. identify the school-related and teacher-related factors that influenced teachers' decision to stay in or leave their current school.
6. use the integrated findings as basis for a Faculty Development Plan for private school settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent literature shows strong agreement that teacher retention is shaped by multiple organizational conditions rather than by one issue alone. In Philippine private-school research, compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth consistently appear as important influences on teachers' intention to stay (Anog et al., 2024; Saldevia & Pedroso, 2025; Ubal, 2025). International work supports the same pattern, but it also shows that these factors do not always operate in the same way across settings. Some studies identify working conditions as the strongest direct driver, while others emphasize leadership, compensation, or development opportunities depending on the school context (Toropova et al., 2021; Eryilmaz et al., 2025).

This variation suggests that retention should be examined as a context-sensitive and multidimensional outcome. Compensation affects financial security and perceived fairness, yet compensation alone rarely explains why teachers stay. Administrative support shapes trust, voice, and recognition, making leadership a relational condition rather than a simple managerial function. Working conditions influence day-to-day sustainability through workload, climate, resources, and emotional strain. Professional growth strengthens competence, confidence, and future orientation. Taken together, the literature suggests that these areas interact,

which means that a school may perform well in one area while still losing teachers if the broader balance remains weak (Fernandez & Quines, 2023; Gundlach et al., 2024).

The present study extends this body of work in two ways. First, it examines satisfaction and retention together using the same four organizational dimensions, rather than treating them as separate concerns. Second, it uses an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design in provincial private schools, allowing statistical patterns to be interpreted through teachers' lived experiences. In this way, the study responds to a methodological and contextual gap in the literature and offers findings that are directly useful for school-level decision making (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. Quantitative data were gathered and analyzed first to determine levels, relationships, and predictive patterns, and then qualitative data were collected to explain and deepen the statistical results. This design was appropriate because the study examined both measurable school conditions and teachers' lived experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2022; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2021).

Participants and Sampling

The quantitative phase involved 78 teachers from selected private schools in the Schools Division of Silay City. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling and had to be teaching in basic education, hold regular or contractual status, and have at least four years of service in their current school. The group size reflected the full population of teachers in the selected schools who met the inclusion criteria at the time of data gathering. Because the study aimed for criterion-based local understanding rather than statistical generalization, this size was methodologically acceptable for the purpose of the inquiry (Memon et al., 2024).

In the qualitative phase, 15 teachers were selected from the survey respondents through maximum variation sampling. Selection considered their survey scores on satisfaction and retention, together with differences in school level and work context, so that the interviews would capture varied perspectives.

Research Instruments and Validation

The quantitative instrument consisted of a demographic profile, a teacher retention survey, and a teacher satisfaction survey. Retention items were partially adapted from Anog et al. (2024) and refined for the local context, while the satisfaction scale was researcher-made and aligned with the study framework. Both instruments measured the same four domains: compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth. Content validity was established through Lawshe's content validity ratio using nine experts. The average content validity ratio was .858 for retention and .886 for satisfaction. Reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha produced coefficients of .885 for retention and .852 for satisfaction, indicating high internal consistency (Lawshe, 1975).

For the qualitative phase, a 17-item semi-structured interview guide was developed from the quantitative findings. It covered teacher experiences, retention decisions, and recommendations for school support. Its scale-level content validity ratio was .974. Pilot coding by two raters produced constant ratings across all 17 items. Cohen's Kappa was also computed to measure agreement; however, no value was obtained due to the absence of variability in the coding. Since both raters provided identical responses across all items, the data lacked the categorical variation required to compute the statistic. The result showed complete agreement in the pilot classification of themes and confirmed that the coding scheme was clear, well-defined and consistently applied.

Data Collection Procedure

Formal approval was secured from the Schools Division Office and the administrators of participating private schools. In the quantitative phase, the researcher personally administered printed questionnaires to eligible teachers. In the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted face-to-face based on participants' availability. For the qualitative phase, semi-

structured interviews were conducted face-to-face, lasted around 30 to 45 minutes, were audio-recorded with consent, and were translated into English when responses were given in Hiligaynon or mixed language.

Data Analysis

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of teacher retention and teacher satisfaction. Pearson product-moment correlation was used to test the bivariate relationship between satisfaction and retention across the four domains. Multiple linear regression was then used to examine the combined predictive influence of compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth on overall teacher retention. Before interpreting the regression model, the assumptions of linear regression were examined using standard diagnostic outputs. Residual normality was checked using the histogram and normal P–P plot of standardized residuals. Multicollinearity was assessed through tolerance and variance inflation factor values. Homoscedasticity was examined through the scatterplot of standardized residuals against standardized predicted values. Overall, the diagnostic tests indicate that the assumptions required for multiple linear regression were satisfactorily met, supporting the validity and reliability of the regression results in explaining the relationship between teachers' satisfaction and retention.

Qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis using the phases of familiarization, initial coding, theme generation, review, and interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2021). The researcher repeatedly read the transcripts, organized codes through a manual coding matrix, coded meaning units related to the four study domains and emergent ideas, grouped related codes into subthemes and broader themes, and compared patterns across participants with different survey profiles. Credibility and trustworthiness were strengthened through member checking, audit trail procedures, and thick description (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Nowell et al., 2017).

Ethical Considerations

Participation was voluntary in both phases of the study. Teachers were informed of the purpose of the research, their right to withdraw at any time, and the confidential treatment of their responses. Written informed consent was secured. Names and identifying details were removed from transcripts and survey records, and collected data were stored securely for academic use only.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Retention and Satisfaction Across Key Areas

Teacher retention was at a high level across all four areas, with an overall mean of 3.76. Working conditions obtained the highest retention mean (3.99), followed by professional growth (3.85) and administrative support (3.76). Compensation obtained the lowest retention mean (3.42), although it still fell within the high range. Teacher satisfaction was also at a high level overall (3.65). Working conditions again obtained the highest mean (3.82), followed by professional growth (3.77) and administrative support (3.71), while compensation was only moderate (3.31).

Table 1

Summary of Teacher Retention and Teacher Satisfaction Across Key Areas

Key Area	Retention Mean	Retention Interpretation	Satisfaction Mean	Satisfaction Interpretation
Compensation	3.42	High	3.31	Moderate
Administrative Support	3.76	High	3.71	High
Working Conditions	3.99	High	3.82	High
Professional Growth	3.85	High	3.77	High
Overall	3.76	High	3.65	High

The pattern shows that teachers generally viewed their schools positively, especially with respect to work environment, leadership support, and development opportunities. The moderate satisfaction rating for compensation, however, shows that financial concerns remain unresolved. In Herzberg's terms, the schools appear to provide relatively stable hygiene conditions in

most areas, but compensation remains the least satisfying condition and may still weaken morale and long-term security. This result is consistent with literature showing that salary and benefits continue to affect how teachers judge institutional fairness and viability in private-school work (Banu, 2025; Fernandez & Quines, 2023).

Relationship Between Satisfaction and Retention

At the bivariate level, compensation and administrative support showed significant positive relationships with retention. Compensation showed a strong positive correlation ($r = .715$, $p = .030$), while administrative support showed a moderate-to-strong positive correlation ($r = .637$, $p = .048$). Working conditions showed only a negligible, non-significant relationship ($r = .094$, $p = .825$), and professional growth showed a moderate negative but non-significant coefficient ($r = -.403$, $p = .282$). The non-significant coefficients should be interpreted cautiously and not treated as evidence that these areas are unimportant. Overall teacher satisfaction and teacher retention had a very strong and significant positive relationship ($r = .978$, $p = .022$).

Table 2

Correlation Between Teacher Satisfaction and Teacher Retention

Key Area	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Compensation	.715	.030	Significant
Administrative Support	.637	.048	Significant
Working Conditions	.094	.825	Not Significant
Professional Growth	-.403	.282	Not Significant
Overall	.978	.022	Significant

The significant findings for compensation and administrative support suggest that these are the most visible school-based levers connected to teachers' decisions to stay. The result also supports Social Exchange Theory: when teachers perceive fair treatment, supportive leadership, and recognition, they are more likely to respond with stronger commitment to the institution. The non-significant coefficients for working conditions and professional growth do not cancel their importance. Instead, they suggest that these factors may work less as isolated triggers and more as part of a broader institutional package. This interpretation is supported by the multivariate findings that follow.

Predictive Influence of Satisfaction Components

The regression results showed that teacher retention was better explained through the combined influence of school conditions. The model was statistically significant and explained a substantial proportion of the variance in overall teacher retention ($R = .938$, $R^2 = .879$, adjusted $R^2 = .872$, $F = 132.720$, $p < .001$).

Table 3

Regression Model Summary for Overall Teacher Retention

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error	F	p-value
.938	.879	.872	.21272	132.720	< .001

Table 4

Regression Coefficients Predicting Overall Teacher Retention

Predictor	B	Beta	t	p-value
Compensation	0.200	0.261	3.620	.001
Administrative Support	0.222	0.269	2.678	.009
Working Conditions	0.167	0.167	2.840	.006
Professional Growth	0.278	0.342	4.092	< .001

All four satisfaction components significantly predicted retention when examined together. Professional growth had the highest standardized beta ($\beta = .342$), making it the strongest predictor, followed by administrative support ($\beta = .269$), compensation ($\beta = .261$), and working conditions ($\beta = .167$). This finding is important because it shows that retention is shaped not only by what teachers currently receive, but also by whether they can see a future for themselves in the school. The result strongly supports Herzberg's view that growth and advancement deepen commitment beyond the prevention of dissatisfaction.

It also aligns with studies showing that mentoring, training, graduate study support, and career pathways strengthen teacher identity and long-term purpose (Darling-Hammond et al., 2022; Eryilmaz et al., 2025; See et al., 2020).

The Qualitative Findings section presents the results of the in-depth interviews conducted with selected teachers from private schools. The findings are organized into three thematic sections, each followed by themes that capture teachers' lived experiences, retention decisions, and suggested school supports. These findings deepen the quantitative results by showing how teachers interpret compensation, administrative support, working conditions, and professional growth in their everyday professional lives.

1. Teachers' Experiences Related to Job Satisfaction and Retention

Theme 1: Fulfillment from Student Growth and Emotional Reward

Teachers described student growth as one of the most rewarding parts of their work. They explained that seeing learners understand lessons, improve in confidence, and show positive values gave meaning to their daily efforts and strengthened their desire to continue teaching. For them, fulfillment came not only from academic outcomes but also from witnessing the holistic development of their students. One teacher shared: *"The aspects of my work in this school that make me feel fulfilled and motivated as a teacher are when the students learn something from me, the simple 'thank you' and 'I know this,' make my heart full and fulfilled."* (R1)

Theme 2: Sense of Belonging and Supportive School Community

Another important source of satisfaction was the sense of belonging teachers felt within a supportive school community. Participants valued collegial relationships, mutual help, and a family-like atmosphere that reduced stress and made school life more manageable and meaningful. One teacher mentioned: *"The school as a community has been very supportive. My co-teachers and the administrators are always willing to extend a helping hand when needed."* (R2)

Theme 3: Vocational Purpose and Professional Pride

Teachers also viewed teaching as more than employment. They described it as a vocation that gave them purpose, direction, and a strong sense of professional identity, which helped sustain commitment despite challenges. One teacher said: *"Teaching is more than a profession; it is a vocation."* (R4)

Theme 4: Personal and Professional Growth Through Teaching

Participants further shared that teaching helped them grow both personally and professionally. Their school experiences allowed them to develop patience, confidence, and instructional skill, reinforcing the idea that staying in the profession was also a path for self-development. One participant explained: *"In my almost seven years here, I find it both a rewarding and challenging journey. Overall, my experience has taught me to grow professionally and personally."* (R1)

These themes show that teachers' job satisfaction is strongly shaped by intrinsic fulfillment, supportive relationships, vocational purpose, and opportunities for growth. Similar findings have been reported in studies emphasizing meaningful teaching experiences, positive school environments, and development opportunities as important supports for long-term commitment (Toropova et al., 2021; Eryilmaz et al., 2025).

2. School- and Teacher-Related Factors Influencing Retention Decisions

Theme 1: Compensation, Financial Sustainability, and Job Security

Compensation emerged as a major factor in teachers' retention decisions. Participants connected salary, benefits, and financial stability to their ability to remain in the school long term. They viewed compensation not only as financial support but also as an indicator of whether the institution values their service. A teacher said: *"Salary has been a great challenge for us professionals. If the salary is not competitive, it is the best way to look for a greener pasture."* (R5)

Theme 2: Administrative Support, Fair Treatment, and Recognition

Leadership support was repeatedly described as central to retention. Teachers emphasized that fair, approachable, and responsive administrators create trust, strengthen morale, and make workplace challenges more manageable. Recognition and open communication

helped them feel heard and valued. A teacher pointed out: *"At present, leadership support has the greatest influence on my decision to stay because feeling valued, heard, and guided by administrators directly affects my motivation and job satisfaction."* (R9)

Theme 3: Working Conditions and Organizational Environment

Teachers also described the working environment as one of the most immediate influences on their decision to stay. A supportive, collaborative, and healthy school culture helped them focus on teaching, manage stress, and sustain commitment, while excessive

workload and negative work conditions were viewed as possible reasons for leaving. A participant said: *"At present, the working environment has the greatest influence on my decision to stay. A supportive and positive environment, along with a collaborative school culture, allows me to focus on teaching and feel fulfilled."* (R14)

Theme 4: Professional Growth Opportunities

Professional growth was another major retention factor. Participants highlighted mentoring, training, graduate studies, and career development as important sources of competence, confidence, and long-term engagement. They also noted that limited growth opportunities could push them to consider other options. A teacher mentioned: *"Professional growth and opportunities encourage me to stay in the school."* (R4)

Theme 5: Work-Life Balance and Personal Sustainability

Beyond school-based conditions, teachers stressed that personal sustainability also shapes retention. Health, workload, stress, and family responsibilities influenced whether they felt capable of remaining in the institution over time. These responses show that retention is not only structural but also deeply personal. A teacher said: *"I might seriously consider leaving if there is ongoing unfair treatment, lack of support from administrators, or excessive workload that leads to burnout."* (R6)

Taken together, these findings show that retention decisions are shaped by both institutional conditions and teachers' personal realities. The themes align with studies that identify compensation, leadership, working conditions, and growth opportunities as key factors influencing teacher satisfaction and retention (Anog et al., 2024; Sebulen & Jimenez, 2024; Toropova et al., 2021).

3. Recommendations for Enhancing Teacher Satisfaction and Retention

Theme 1: Competitive Compensation and Benefits

Teachers recommended fair and more competitive compensation as a direct way to improve retention. They emphasized that better salaries and benefits would reduce financial strain, acknowledge teachers' work, and encourage long-term commitment. One participant expressed: *"Offer a higher salary rate for teachers."* (R7)

Theme 2: Leadership Support and Recognition

Participants also recommended stronger leadership support marked by fair treatment, clear communication, and recognition of teacher contributions. They viewed supportive leadership as essential for building trust and maintaining a school environment that teachers would want to remain in. A respondent shortly said: *“Compensation and leadership support are important.”* (R10)

Theme 3: Professional Growth and Development Opportunities

Continuous professional development was identified as another important recommendation. Teachers expressed the need for more training, mentoring, and career advancement opportunities that would help them improve their practice and feel that the school is investing in their future. A teacher shared: *“Based on my experience, the school should prioritize improving compensation and benefits, providing more professional growth opportunities, and strengthening leadership support through clear communication and recognition.”* (R9)

Theme 4: Positive Work Environment and Adequate Resources

Teachers further recommended a more supportive and well-resourced work environment. Adequate facilities, instructional resources, healthy relationships, and manageable workload were seen as necessary for sustaining both professional effectiveness and well-being.

A teacher suggested: *“For me, the school should improve its facilities for teachers to adapt to the changes in classroom instruction, and if possible, increase the salaries of the faculty so that the teachers will decide to stay.”* (R2)

Theme 5: Holistic Approach to Retention

Finally, participants emphasized that retention should be addressed through a holistic approach. Rather than focusing on one concern at a time, they believed schools should address compensation, leadership, working conditions, and professional growth in a coordinated

manner. A teacher expressed: *“A balanced approach that values teachers’ welfare, growth, and work environment will significantly improve satisfaction and retention.”* (R6)

Overall, the recommendations expressed by participants support an integrated school response to retention. This is consistent with literature showing that effective teacher retention strategies combine financial support, leadership practices, development opportunities, and healthy organizational culture (Banu, 2025; Busico et al., 2026; Fernandez & Quines, 2023).

Table 5

Main Thematic Sections and Themes Related to Teacher Satisfaction and Retention

Main Thematic Sections	Themes
Teachers’ Experiences Related to Job Satisfaction and Retention	Fulfillment from Student Growth and Emotional Reward Sense of Belonging and Supportive School Community Vocational Purpose and Professional Pride Personal and Professional Growth Through Teaching
School- and Teacher-Related Factors Influencing Retention Decisions	Compensation, Financial Sustainability, and Job Security Administrative Support, Fair Treatment, and Recognition Working Conditions and Organizational Environment Professional Growth Opportunities Work-Life Balance and Personal Sustainability
Recommendations for Enhancing Teacher Satisfaction and Retention	Competitive Compensation and Benefits Leadership Support and Recognition Professional Growth and Development Opportunities Positive Work Environment and Adequate Resources Holistic Approach to Retention

Teachers described student growth, collegial support, and teaching as a vocation as strong sources of satisfaction. These narratives show that retention is partly anchored in meaning, not only in organizational arrangements. At the same time, participants spoke clearly about institutional conditions. Compensation was linked to financial sustainability and feelings of being valued. Administrative support was associated with fairness, trust, dialogue, and recognition. Working conditions shaped daily well-being through workload, school climate, and available resources. Professional growth signaled that the institution invested in teachers' future. Work-life balance also appeared as an important concern, especially when workload and stress threatened personal sustainability.

The qualitative results help explain the unexpected bivariate findings. Working conditions and professional growth were not significant as stand-alone correlations, yet teachers repeatedly described both as essential to long-term commitment. This suggests that these factors may matter less as isolated variables and more as enabling conditions that strengthen the effect of other supports. Put differently, teachers may remain not because one factor is excellent, but because the school offers a workable balance of financial support, leadership, environment, and growth.

When the quantitative and qualitative results are read together, teacher retention in private schools appears multidimensional and human-centered. Compensation remained the weakest area in terms of satisfaction, but teachers still connected fair compensation with institutional recognition and long-term security. Administrative support shaped trust and belonging, which supports Social Exchange Theory. Professional growth emerged as the strongest predictor of retention in the regression model, which supports Herzberg's argument that advancement and development deepen commitment. Working conditions, although not significant in the bivariate test,

remained central in teachers' narratives because they shaped the broader environment in which other supports were experienced. These integrated findings show that private schools are more likely to retain teachers when support is coordinated rather than fragmented.

CONCLUSION

The study contributes to the teacher-retention literature by showing that satisfaction and retention can be examined through the same organizational dimensions within a provincial private-school context. It also shows the value of an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design in clarifying why statistical patterns emerge.

Substantively, the findings indicate that compensation and administrative support are the clearest direct correlates of retention at the bivariate level, while all four satisfaction dimensions significantly predict retention when examined together. Professional growth emerged as the strongest predictor, showing that teachers are more likely to remain when they see future development within the institution.

The qualitative strand adds an important insight: teachers do not stay because of organizational conditions alone. They also stay because of meaning, belonging, vocation, and personal sustainability. For this reason, teacher retention in private schools should be understood as both structural and human. This conclusion has practical value for school leaders and policy makers who need retention strategies that address financial, relational, organizational, and developmental needs at the same time.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations below are grouped into policy, practice, and future research to align more directly with the study findings.

Policy

1. Private-school governing bodies may conduct periodic salary benchmarking and compensation review within institutional capacity, since compensation was the least satisfying area, yet remained significantly related to retention.
2. Education authorities and school associations may support private schools through policy dialogue and technical guidance on teacher-support standards, especially for provincial schools operating with limited resources.

Practice

1. School leaders may strengthen administrative support through structured teacher–administrator dialogue, timely guidance, fair decision-making, and consistent recognition of teacher contributions.
2. Schools may establish or strengthen mentoring, training, graduate-study support, and clearer career pathways because professional growth emerged as the strongest predictor of retention in the regression model.
3. Schools may review workload distribution, protect work–life balance, and improve access to facilities and instructional resources so that working conditions continue to support teacher well-being.
4. Private schools may use the proposed Faculty Development Plan as a coordinated framework that links compensation practices, leadership support, working conditions, professional growth, and regular feedback mechanisms.

Future Research

1. Future studies may replicate the inquiry in other private-school settings, include additional predictors, and use longer observation periods to test whether the same patterns hold across time and context.
2. Future researchers may also report full regression diagnostics and use respondent-level composite correlations to strengthen statistical transparency in similar retention studies.

Conflict of Interest

The authors must disclose any potential conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, that could be perceived to influence the work.

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